

Supplementary Materials

Foundations of Narrative Bibliometrics

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This supplementary material serves as an exemplary showcase of how narrative bibliometrics can be employed to effectively communicate scientific achievements. As detailed in the document "[Foundations of Narrative Bibliometrics](#)," this emerging approach addresses the evolving landscape of scientific assessment. Influenced by manifestos such as DORA and CoARA, narrative bibliometrics promotes ethical and responsible practices within academia, advocating for a blend of quantitative and qualitative evaluation methods. This methodological shift is underscored by the integration of the Narrative Curriculum, which facilitates the description of the complexity and context of academic contributions. Narrative bibliometrics uses bibliometric indicators to craft compelling narratives that defend and elucidate the scientific curriculum and individual contributions within scientific evaluation processes. By presenting a non-exhaustive array of sources, indicators, and practical cases, Table SM1 illustrates how narrative bibliometrics can be effectively applied across various evaluation contexts, thereby contributing to the responsible usage of bibliometric indicators and aiding evaluators and researchers in articulating the value of their work. This approach not only provides a statistical understanding but also connects these data with real and impactful narratives, enhancing the visibility and impact of research within and beyond the academic community.

Table SM1. Examples of common indicators and their linked narratives for the defense of scientific contributions within the framework

Indicator	Narrative
<p>Total Citations (with and without self-citations)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Evidence Scientific impact</p>	<p><i>The contribution has been widely recognized in the scientific community, as demonstrated by its impact in the Web of Science Core Collection with a total of 40 citations, highlighting the absence of significant self-citations. Among the European and Spanish institutions that have cited this work are Stanford University with 9 citations, the University of Milan with 6, and the University of Barcelona, each contributing 5 citations. The research has also caught the attention of organizations like the Karolinska Institute (4 citations) and the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) with 3 citations. Its interdisciplinary nature is reflected in citations from areas such as "Genetics and Heredity" (12 citations), "Pharmacology and Toxicology" (8 citations), and "Public and Environmental Health" (6 citations). Additionally, its relevance is evidenced by how it has been predominantly cited in the results sections (10 citations) and methodology (5 citations) in related literature, underscoring its impact on the formulation of new research and the interpretation of scientific data.</i></p>
<p>Category Normalized Citation Impact (CNCI)</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Evidence Scientific impact</p>	<p><i>The work, indexed in the thematic category of "Nutrition and Dietetics", has shown a significantly higher impact than the average in its field. With a total of 28 citations received, this study stands out notably compared to the average number of citations expected for works of similar category and publication year. For the year 2021, the expected citation figure for an average work in the "Nutrition and Dietetics" category is 8.10. Comparing this average with the 28 citations obtained by our work, it shows exceptional performance, almost tripling the number of citations that would normally be expected for an article in this thematic category. The Category Normalized Citation Impact (CNCI) quantifies this observation. It is calculated by dividing the total number of citations received by the number of expected citations, in this case, 28 divided by 8.10, resulting in a CNCI of 3.46. This value underscores that the work has not only met but significantly exceeded citation expectations, placing it in a prominent position within its thematic area.</i></p>

<p>Percentile</p> <p>Evidence Scientific impact</p>	<p><i>This article on deep learning and its application in complex pattern recognition, published in the "Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research", has to date accumulated 150 citations. It has reached a high 97th percentile in Scopus in the "Artificial Intelligence" category, meaning it is above 97% of publications in citations or in other words, in the top 3% of the most cited publications in its area in the year of its publication, highlighting its impact in such a competitive field. Notably, the low value of self-citations, only 5% of the citations, underscores the quality and independent relevance of the research. This article has been cited by various leading institutions, including MIT and Stanford University, reflecting its broad acceptance and recognition in the global scientific community. Among the citations received, 30 come from articles focused on computational neuroscience, demonstrating its interdisciplinarity and the wide range of applications of its findings.</i></p>
<p>Reviews</p> <p>Evidence Scientific impact</p>	<p><i>The book has been the subject of three distinguished critical reviews compiled in Dialnet. These reviews were carried out by experts in European history, including Dr. Alberto Ruiz from the University of Heidelberg, Dr. María López from the Sorbonne University, and Dr. Giuseppe Conti from the University of Rome. Dr. Ruiz in his review emphasizes: "This work redefines our understanding of the Renaissance, masterfully integrating cultural, political, and social perspectives." Dr. López, for her part, highlights: "Fernández not only offers a captivating narrative but also a profound critical analysis, establishing new paradigms in Renaissance studies." These evaluations highlight the analytical depth and unique contribution of the book to historical knowledge, underlining its significance in academia.</i></p>
<p>Journal Impact Factor (JIF)</p> <p>Evidence Medium relevance</p>	<p><i>The article published in "Scientometrics" presents a unique case, being indexed in the Journal Citation Reports in both Information Science & Library Science (ISLS) in the SSCI and Computer Science, Interdisciplinary Applications in the SCIE. The JIF of the journal in the year of the article's publication, according to the Journal Citation Reports, was 4.5 in 2022, the year the article was published. This JIF is calculated based on the division of the total number of citations in the year for articles published in the two previous years, 3249 citations, by the total number of publishable articles in those years, 831, reflecting the most recent impact of its publications. The journal Scientometrics is the oldest in our field and was founded in 1978 by Tibor Braun, currently edited and managed by Springer and has been continuously indexed in the Social Science Citation Index since then.</i></p>
<p>Journal Quartile and position</p> <p>Evidence Medium relevance</p>	<p><i>The manuscript was submitted to this journal due to the progression and good impact it has achieved over the last few years, making it a reference journal in its field as shown in Figure 1. It can be seen that in the year of the work's publication, it was in position 28 out of 70 in the CHEMISTRY ANALYTICAL category. Following 2007, the journal began an ascent in its impact and scientific influence, reaching the first quartile by 2009 (position 17 out of 70) and has been indexed uninterruptedly in the same since 2011. Since 2013, it has also always been among the top ten journals in CHEMISTRY ANALYTICAL. Therefore, we are looking at a journal well regarded by the scientific community as evidenced not only by positional indicators but also by the excellent evolution of its Impact Factor: 2016 Position 8 out of 83 (IF=7.803), 2015 (IF=6.764), 2014 (IF=5.538), 2013 (IF=5.463), 2012 (IF=4.743), 2011 (IF=4.182), 2010 (IF=3.609), 2009 (IF=3.184).</i></p>
<p>Social media mentions</p> <p>Evidence Social attention</p>	<p><i>A study on innovative therapies for cardiovascular diseases, published in the "Journal of Clinical Medicine", has generated broad discussion on social media, reaching 190 mentions on Twitter and 78 on Facebook. Using Altmetric.com (geographical breakdown), it is observed that 60% of users from country X who shared the study are from countries outside the study's country of origin, including the United States, the United Kingdom, and Australia. Also, it indicates that the audience of the accounts mentioning us (demographical breakdown) corresponds mainly to the general public (45%) and scientific community (32%) with a small percentage (10%) of science communicators (journalists, bloggers, editors). On Facebook, through PlumX, it is noted that the mentions predominantly come from groups of health professionals and patients interested in medical advancements, 80% of the users, underscoring the practical relevance and reach of the study. Common phrases in the posts on both social networks include "significant advancement in cardiology" and "hope for patients with heart diseases", demonstrating the emotional and professional resonance of the study.</i></p>
<p>News mentions</p> <p>Evidence Social attention</p>	<p><i>This study on innovative therapies for cardiovascular diseases has captured the attention of the media. According to Altmetric.com, it has received a total of 30 mentions in 23 different media outlets in the last 11 months. Of the 30 mentions received, 75% of the media outlets are international, finding prestigious media such as "The Guardian", "CNN", and "The New York Times" highlighting the potential of the therapy to change the treatment paradigm for cardiovascular diseases. Some of these media have referred to our work as "Cardio Care Revolution: New Therapy to Alter Treatment Landscape" (Le Monde Digital, 27/05/2022) or "Transforming Heart Health: Novel Therapy Challenges Old Methods" (Reuters Online, 28/05/2022). These articles not only inform about the study but also contextualize it within the current challenges of medicine, offering perspectives from experts in the field and patients, increasing public understanding and interest in the research.</i></p>

<p>Policy report mentions</p> <p>Evidence Social attention</p>	<p><i>This study on the configuration of new urban spaces has been mentioned four times in public reports (policy documents), we want to highlight its mention in the reports “Delivering Climate Resilient Cities Using a Systems Approach” from the World Economic Forum (2022) which highlights our proposal with the phrase “One paradigmatic system-wide approach that has received significant interest during the COVID-19 pandemic is the “15-minute city”; it has also been mentioned in the “Reference Guide for Climate-Smart Public Investment” from the World Bank (2022) where it is noted “The ‘15-minute city’ represents a magnificent and transformative urban development concept, foreseen as a pivotal model for the future of sustainable and efficient city living”. We must note that some political parties are already incorporating some of their proposals into their political programs, for example, Más Madrid explicitly mentions our publication in their book “Madrid, city of the 15 minutes. This mention in reports is causing requests by seven provincial capitals in Spain for consultancy reports to analyze the feasibility of their cities to our proposal. The information is verifiable through Altmetric, PlumX, and Overton. Also, the reports are available in references 1, 2, 5, and 8.</i></p>
<p>Wikipedia mentions</p> <p>Evidence Social attention</p>	<p><i>Our work on Roman settlements in southern Spain, previously mentioned, has also been cited in 8 Wikipedia articles. 50% are articles from the English edition of Wikipedia and the other half are 2 articles from the Spanish Wikipedia and 2 from the French Wikipedia. Its reference in the article “Roman settlements in Europe”, which is approximately 6000 words long and has a content quality rating of C, thereby acknowledging the level of development of the article. This mention in Wikipedia not only increases the visibility of the study among the general public but also validates its relevance and accuracy in an educational and disseminative context.</i></p>
<p>Mendeley readers</p> <p>Evidence Usage and Visibility</p>	<p><i>As recorded, the study has been added to the personal libraries of 250 users on Mendeley, with a detailed analysis revealing that approximately 40% of these readers are from the United States, followed by 20% from the United Kingdom and 10% from Germany. Nearly half of all readers are students (undergraduate, master’s, and doctoral), highlighting its importance in educational contexts. Furthermore, 45% of the readers belong to the field of Health Sciences and 20% to Social Sciences. These data not only reflect the broad interest and relevance of the study but also demonstrate its interdisciplinary impact and its ability to attract a diverse audience of researchers and professionals in various health-related fields.</i></p>
<p>Academic links</p> <p>Evidence Usage and Visibility</p>	<p><i>The publication has been mentioned on 25 academic websites. These include 20 renowned academic blogs and 5 scientific dissemination sites. A blog managed by Stanford University’s computer science department (Progress in Artificial Intelligence) discusses in detail the implications of the algorithms presented in the article, highlighting their potential to transform the analysis of large datasets across various fields, from medicine to economics. Another scientific dissemination site, known for its focus on artificial intelligence (AI Everyone), offers an accessible overview of the article, focusing on how the algorithms can be used to improve data processing efficiency. These links not only increase the article’s visibility but also underline its applicability across multiple areas of computing and technology. The fact that the article is discussed and analyzed in these diverse forums indicates its significance in the field of data science and its ability to influence the future development of machine learning technology.</i></p>
<p>Downloads</p> <p>Evidence Usage and Visibility</p>	<p><i>The recent article in PLOS ONE has generated significant interest in the scientific community and among the general public. In just one month after its publication, it recorded 3223 visits and 1503 PDF downloads, indicating that nearly half of the visitors downloaded the complete article, reflecting significant interest in its findings. Additionally, 50% of the downloads occurred consistently over the last three months, with an average of 250 downloads per month. The article’s accessibility, facilitated by PLOS ONE’s open access (Gold), has contributed to this broad dissemination. This trend suggests that the article is of great interest not only to researchers in biology and ecology but also to educators, students, and a broader audience interested in topics such as marine conservation and genetics.</i></p>
<p>Presence in libraries</p> <p>Evidence Usage and Visibility</p>	<p><i>This book is available in 47 national and international libraries, according to WorldCat and the collective catalog REBIUN. Of these, 30 are university libraries in Spain. A detailed analysis reveals that approximately 20% of these libraries are located in the Community of Madrid and Catalonia, and another 20% in Andalusia, demonstrating the book’s strong presence in Spain’s main academic regions, indicative of its importance and acceptance in the philosophical and academic realm. The concentration of copies in renowned universities such as the Complutense University of Madrid and the University of Barcelona, as well as in regional institutions, underscores its relevance in teaching and studying contemporary philosophy in Spain. Internationally, it is present in 7 French libraries, including the Bibliothèque interuniversitaire de la Sorbonne (BIS) and the Bibliothèque Universitaire de Strasbourg, and in three libraries in the United Kingdom, such as the Bodleian Library at the University of Oxford and the British Library. This wide presence in university libraries suggests the book is a reference work in philosophy and ethics courses, evidencing its influence on the training of future generations of philosophers and thinkers.</i></p>